

**PROCEDURES OF PRIVATE SECURITY AGENCIES FOR THE SAFE
HOLDING OF SPORTS EVENTS, PUBLIC ASSEMBLIES AND
MANIFESTATIONS**

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Abstract

In the last two decades, the Republic of North Macedonia has witnessed a gradual expansion and progress in the democratization of society. As an inevitable consequence of the transition, the emergence and operation of a larger number of political parties, privatization, the emergence of a large number of socially endangered groups of citizens, and the military conflict, as well as the continuous political struggle for supremacy and the large number of political and social protests, have occurred. All this led to an increase in the number of cases of violent, demolishing, and destructive behavior of citizens, which most often ended with clashes between citizens and the police in public places. However, organized gatherings of citizens also took place on other occasions, in a sports, musical, solidarity, or other context, which still require services to maintain order and peace. Such a situation has also been transferred to the holding of various cultural and sports events. There has been a need to involve “police” services that will maintain order before, during, and after the gatherings, while the police services will react in specific situations where they are not able to establish order and the situation gets out of control. Until then, security personnel, the so-called police services, are organized to monitor and maintain the situation within the framework of normality.

The paper will cover the standard procedures for security negotiation, planning, preparation, implementation, and post-implementation procedures of an event where private security will be engaged, in order to harmonize and simplify procedures and achieve efficiency, effectiveness, and quality implementation of tasks.

Keywords: private security, security plan, security measures

Introduction

Private security agencies, in accordance with the Law on Private Security¹, have the legal opportunity to secure public gatherings, sports competitions, and events. This right is given to agencies that provide services. In accordance with the conceptual and categorical apparatus in the law, “securing public gatherings and other events” is physical security with private security workers and with the use of technical means for the purpose of maintaining public order at public gatherings, sports competitions, cultural, entertainment, religious, humanitarian, social, political, economic, and other events.

The Law on Private Security has regulated this activity and stipulates that a legal entity that provides private security in the form of providing services may perform work to maintain public order at public gatherings, sports competitions, cultural, entertainment, religious, humanitarian, social, political, economic, and other events with security workers and using technical means and devices in accordance with the regulations on public gatherings and preventing violence at sports competitions. Security workers wear work clothes and vests with reflective stripes on which the inscription “Security” is written. During the performance of work to maintain public order, security workers may not regulate traffic. Security workers perform their work without firearms.

When a legal entity maintains public order at a public gathering or event and for that purpose engages more than five security workers, the responsible person in the legal entity is obliged to develop a plan for securing the event, which is submitted to the Ministry of Internal Affairs in the area where the public gathering or event is being held, no later than 48 hours before the gathering or event. The plan must contain: the place and time of the public gathering or event being secured; the number and schedule of the security workers engaged; data on the person who will manage the security workers during the holding of the public gathering or event; and the means of communication with this person.

Preparation and implementation of Event Security

Event security refers to security when five (5) or more security workers are engaged. Security refers to public gatherings, manifestations in the fields of culture, entertainment, religious, economic, political, etc. gatherings of a large number of citizens, or sports competitions. Security refers to the physical and technical protection of a certain space (open or closed), public order and peace, as well as individuals (from politics, economics, cultural or entertainment life – VIPs).

The procedure for planning, performing and executing security begins with a submitted (oral or written) request from a client (natural or legal entity) for the realization of a service –event security. The client most often appears as the organizer of the event, part of the organizational structure, members of a certain organization (governmental or non-governmental), religious communities, trade union organizations, political parties, wings of political entities, federations, clubs, individuals, etc. This is followed by the organization of

¹Law on Private Security (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia” No. 166/12), Law on Amending and Supplementing the Law on Private Security (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia” No. 164/13), Law on Amending and Supplementing the Law on Private Security (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia” No. 148/15), Law on Amending and Supplementing the Law on Private Security (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia” No. 193/15), Law on Amending and Supplementing the Law on Private Security (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia” No. 55/16) and Law on Amending the Law on Private Security (“Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia” No. 302/20).

a meeting with the client, which should be attended by authorized person(s) from the service requester, with authorization to negotiate and sign a service agreement, and representatives from the security agency, also authorized to negotiate and sign service agreements.

At the meeting, in addition to the introductory part and the definition of the service in terms of the type of event, required resources, and the type and content of the service, it is necessary to provide data about the client. The data about the client should not be secret or conspiratorial, but should accurately indicate who and what the client is, in order to be able to realize the service of event security. Identification data are provided by the responsible person appointed by the client to organize and realize the event, in order to confirm the seriousness of the request. The name and surname of the person present are required, as well as the name of the legal entity-client, the tax number (EDB), the personal identification number (EMBG) of the person responsible, bank account, and the method and type of further communication. It would be advisable if, already at the meeting, the client designates a person for further communication for the necessary coordination and agreement of details.

At the meeting, the client (organizer, service customer) is obliged to present all data about the planned event for which security services are being requested. It is important to determine the type of event, whether it is a sports competition, cultural, entertainment, religious, economic, political, or other event. Determining the exact date and time is very important, as is the planned time interval for the duration of the event. The specific agenda of the event may be provided immediately at the meeting or later within the framework of coordination communication, with the attendees indicated in the official part, as well as possible other attendees who may come to the event and who are of particular importance. Above all, it is important to determine their role (conference participant, person who will officially open the event, guest of honor, etc.). This information is necessary for further planning and deployment of security forces, particularly in reinforcing human and technical resources at locations where important persons are present, who may influence the event, calm the attendees, or, conversely, provoke inappropriate behavior.

Important elements that need to be obtained as basic knowledge are:

- Why is the event being held? Here, the reasons corresponding to the importance and vitality of holding the event must be identified;
- Who will be the stakeholders of the event? These include internal stakeholders, such as the board of directors, management, staff, and the audience or guests, as well as external stakeholders, such as the media and politicians;
- When will the event be held? Is there enough time to research and plan the event?
- Where will the event be held? The choice of venue must represent the best possible compromise between the organizational needs of the event, the comfort of the visitors, accessibility and costs;
- What is the content of the event or the purpose of the event?

Additional questions that need to be clarified are:

- Who are the participants in the event – individuals, groups, teams, associations;
- Data on the participants of the event – previous participations, destructive scenarios, abnormal behaviors, provocative behavior, calls for destruction, additional plans or elaborated scenarios for disruption of events or injury to the space or the people present;
- Method of attendance – tickets, invitations, passes, identification documents, free access and attendance, etc.;
- Expected number of people present, according to the client's knowledge or the capacity of the facility where the event will be held;

- Presence of VIPs who enjoy security from official state bodies, personal security, or other types of security; people who are important for the event but do not enjoy additional security, their companions, etc.;

- Presence of accredited journalistic teams with cameras, in person, or the presence of people from other public media, freelance reporters, etc.;

- The presence of police forces, fire brigades, and medical services is an important part of the knowledge about the event, because they also require an appropriate plan and resources for deployment, as well as an agreement on action and procedures in cases of disruption of public order and peace at the event;

- If it is a sports match, important information includes the presence of the visiting team (their number), their supporters, fans, relatives, and friends of the players, etc.

- Important information is information about the space where the event will take place (if it is an open space), the facility (if it is an indoor facility), or another place that could be a combination of open and indoor space. In order to make a realistic and optimal assessment of needs, to determine the number of people, resources and equipment, it is very important to obtain the following data about the space/facility:

- Location of the event, the limits within which the planned attendees will move or be present, the method of marking the space, access roads and the method of organizing entry into the limited space, agreement on expansion if the space becomes too small for all attendees, and the method and location of reception/entry and exit from the event;

- If it is a closed facility, what is the size of the facility? In principle, all built facilities intended for occasional or permanent presence of people, in accordance with their construction documentation, have a maximum permitted number of occupants. Any exceeding of this number carries a risk for everyone. Certain facilities have special areas for accommodating attendees that may be limited, fenced or arranged on floors, so information is needed on the number of floors/storeys, the capacity of each separate and accessible area for entry and exit, and, of course, additional measures in case of the need for evacuation for various reasons.

- Configuration and placement of the facility/space in relation to access roads, other critical infrastructure facilities, family homes, or other privately owned facilities or spaces, damage to which could cause major harm to facilities, people or safety in general. This includes proximity to potentially dangerous areas in situations of group euphoria or the creation of a “stampede” (rivers, lakes, excavated deep areas, military or police facilities, etc.). These aspects should be especially emphasized for the purpose of deploying a sufficient number of personnel and equipment in order to prevent injuries or loss of life, as well as irreparable damage to property or general safety;

- Infrastructure in and around the facility. Are there other business facilities or equipment within the same facility where the event will be held;

- Layout of the premises – press centers, meeting rooms, VIP box, guest team, guest spectators, etc.

The data obtained about the space that will be subject to security, the number and profile of attendees, and the type of event form the basis for building a security assessment for the event. In this context, the responsible persons begin by developing the assessment. The data about the event itself require predicting the optimal number of people who will be engaged. There are situations in which the client himself determines how many people will be needed to secure the event, but such a practice should be avoided before a security assessment is conducted by the security agency.

Clients/organizers of event, particularly when the event is profitable for the client requesting security services (sports competitions, concert), often make their own assessment according to the principle of engaging fewer people and fewer resources for the security agency. However, they often fail to take into account that once the security agency concludes a contract for securing the event, in accordance with its provisions, responsibility for all security-related aspects is assumed by the security agency. This approach may be acceptable when the event is of “low” risk and there is no anticipated disruption of the planned agenda. However, if the client acts in this manner and, for various reasons, does not believe in or is not aware of certain “black” scenarios, the security agency may not be able to respond appropriately to a situation that arises. In such cases, when the organizer is decisive and convinced that no such scenarios exist, it would be advisable to foresee a provision in the contract itself in order to avoid bearing responsibility, in accordance with the positive legal regulations of the Republic of North Macedonia.

Therefore, the best approach is to obtain data from the client and for the security agency itself to conduct a security assessment, including information about the broader security situation in the region and the country, current events, and information received about planned security violations, in general, throughout the territory of the country, in specific areas, or at the event itself. A serious approach is required in building such an assessment. It should include:

- Required resources
- An estimate of the required number of security workers to carry out the security;
- Required material and technical means;
- Methods and means of communication, internally and externally;
- Preparation of passes or other necessary documents for identifying security personnel (in addition to vests bearing the inscription “Security”, which is a legal obligation);
- Additional forces kept in reserve, with material and technical means, for action in situations where the foreseen and engaged resources show weaknesses or an inability to control the situation due to unforeseen circumstances.

Consequently, the totality of actions that precede or follow the realization of the event must be planned in advance, because it is incorrect to plan only the holding of the event itself. The obligation of the security agency is to deploy its forces a sufficient period of time before the start and holding of the event. Even in the case of an event with a “high” risk, deployment may take place one or several days before the event, all with the aim of achieving a complete overview of the activities of all persons present during those time intervals, who may have specific constructive or destructive intentions. In this context, it is necessary to clearly agree on these matters with the client/organizer, with clear guidelines and pre-agreed procedures, in order to avoid unwanted conflict situations with persons who carry out logistics and event preparation activities and are not part of the security agency.

For this purpose, external security is organized. The space intended for holding the event (open space), if large, must be divided into several zones, to which an appropriate number of security personnel will be assigned and given specific tasks for handling and controlling the space. Any unusual situation or action by attendees of any kind must be immediately reported to the responsible person, even if the event has not yet started or there is still significant time before the official beginning of the scheduled part of the event. Such procedures are monitored by appropriately positioned personnel who react to any inappropriate behavior or action, primarily through patrol activities.

Internal security involves planning an appropriate number of personnel who will be assigned tasks for the realization of the event in locations that are considered critical for the safe conduct of the event within the facility itself or within the precisely designated space if it is an open area. In accordance with several parameters and criteria, an optimal number of security personnel is assigned. Their schedule, concentration, type of deployment model, and manner of action will be explained later as part of the tactical approach.

The control of the means of transportation used to transport officials specified in the agenda, as well as other persons present at the event, may be classified as external security. However, due to its specifics, this area requires separate planning, including access methods, routines, arrival and departure routes, and securing of the vehicles. This is regulated by agreement with the client and adequately planned in the operational plan for the realization of the event. What is prohibited by the Law on Private Security is the regulation of traffic by security agency personnel. This means that security personnel may not replace traffic police officers, who are the only ones authorized to regulate traffic in all areas.

For the purposes of security agencies, and for better understanding, it is necessary to explain what traffic control and regulation include. Since the law prohibits security personnel from regulating traffic, they may not be stationed on highways, main and regional roads, nor may they give signals to regulate traffic or conduct traffic control. However, in situations where a security agency has a contract for securing an event, security personnel may take measures to regulate and control vehicles within the designated parking area (outer perimeter), assuming full responsibility for that area, but they may not act outside it. Allowing them to regulate traffic outside the designated area would create overlap with the work of the traffic police, leading to confusion among drivers and difficulties in complying with traffic rules and regulations.

Within the designated vehicle parking area, security personnel will have the right and obligation to act according to the situation or instructions of the person responsible for the event and to direct traffic participants to appropriate locations and routes in order to ensure the safe conduct of the event. Such procedures allow priority access and ensure that the vehicles of officials are parked in the safest locations, thereby avoiding unwanted encounters, actions, or incidents.

In coordination with law enforcement institutions, security personnel must be familiar with the procedures implemented by persons who are not in official police uniform. Members of the civilian staff of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the operational staff of the National Security Agency, or other services and agencies, once they identify and legitimize themselves as members of official services, must be allowed access to the external or internal space secured by the security agency. These services may undertake various actions, and at official events attended by persons who enjoy legal personal security, they will certainly carry out counter-sabotage protection measures and inspection of the area. The area subject to inspection may be within the perimeter agreed with the security agency, but it may also be outside it, which is their legal right and obligation.

In such cases, it is necessary to allow them to perform all actions they deem appropriate, even if security personnel from the agency have already been deployed to secure the area. The person responsible for securing the event from the security agency must be informed of their presence. After counter-sabotage or other inspections are completed, these services may either leave their own personnel to secure the area or, in coordination with the responsible person from the security agency, instruct security personnel to pay special attention to specific elements during the event. In such cases, security personnel must act in accordance with the indications or orders received from authorized officials.

In order to ensure complete protection of all persons present at the event, security agency personnel must be familiar with, and trained in, fire protection procedures. All preventive measures provided for in the facility or space must be strictly respected, and any observed deviations must be addressed by warning the responsible persons and pointing out unauthorized actions. Security personnel must also be familiar with the fire extinguishing equipment, including its location, type, distance to other equipment, and the existence of central hydrant system. Preventive fire protection measures must be respected by everyone, including security personnel, members of official services, law enforcement bodies, and citizens.

This paper addresses the totality of fire and explosion protection measures in order to familiarize the management team of security agencies responsible for people and facilities. This will enable them to request sketches and explanations of fire protection systems in facilities where events are planned. The goal is to explicitly state in the service agreement any elements that are not in compliance with the legal fire protection regulations, in order to avoid liability for the agency providing the service, particularly in cases where inadequate conditions could lead to the occurrence or escalation of fires.

Preparation of a Security Plan

The security plan for an event or events must be an act that provides a complete overview of the activities envisaged in the agency's engagement agreement, with designated actions before the start, during, and after the completion of the event, including departure from the event location.

A security plan is understood as an assessment of the security situation in relation to threats to the secured facility or persons, as well as the security measures that will be taken and implemented.

Before initiating the process of securing an event, persons and facilities, a realistic assessment must be made of data concerning phenomena and events related to possible security threats. By monitoring the carriers of threats, their influence, strength, and the means they use, appropriate measures should be developed and implemented to eliminate or remove the circumstances under which such threats arise.

Based on observations and knowledge obtained through conversations and negotiations with the event organizers, first, the existing carriers of threats to the life, health and activities of the organizers and participants (core) of the event are first identified. Then, depending on the nature of the event, political affiliation, or other relevant factors, attitudes and characteristic data, an assessment is made of which forms of security threats and their carriers may appear at the event.

Preventive activity also includes a security assessment of the level of vulnerability of the protected event, including the persons and the facility. Based on this assessment and the identified level of vulnerability, the existing security plan is developed or modified².

The security assessment is prepared in the form of a written document and represents an integral part of the security plan. It presents the current security situation, forecasts future developments, and specifies the tasks and measures necessary to eliminate causes, methods of confrontation, and preventive actions in order to prevent threats to the security of the event, persons, and the facility.

²Stajic, Lj., Pajkovic, D., *System Protection of Persons and Objects*, Faculty of Law, Novi Sad, 2008, p. 86.

A security assessment represents a set of knowledge and conclusions acquired with the participation of relevant entities and evaluated through an appropriate procedure³.

A security assessment is an analytical-synthetic, operational-expert, and most often operational document. The analytical assessment of the security situation refers to the identification and comparative analysis of all negative security events (potential threat carriers, their actions, intentions, and the probability of their action), as well as the assessment of one's own capacities to resolve security challenges. For the preparation of a security assessment, it is essential to ensure an adequate amount of high-quality data, their consistent recording, a unified methodological approach to security data assessment, and comparability of the security situation in the monitored area. This enables the development of conclusions that directly influence the planning, organization and implementation of appropriate security and protection measures. The objective is to neutralize or minimize the likelihood of threats to the security of the event. The security assessment must reflect the real situation, be realistic, and serve as the foundational document of the security plan that defines measures and actions for the protection of people and facilities.

The assessment of the security situation represents a link between the collection, analysis, and processing of data on one side and decision-making on the other, with the aim of preventing violations of the security of specific events.

Due to the type and nature of security, each event is continuously exposed to serious security risks and threats, and the level of danger arising from them varies. Therefore, it is of particular importance to provide conditions that ensure a high level of protection, both for the security personnel involved in the procedure (security workers) and for the general public (persons within the facilities where entry and exit occur, as well as all citizens who are present or may accidentally find themselves at the event location).

The term risk refers to an assumed, expected, forecasted, or possible future action, occurrence, or omission, caused by a person, a technological process, or a natural phenomenon, which under certain conditions, reasons, or circumstances may cause a form of threat to people, property, or other cultural or natural values. Risk should be understood as a condition that precedes the emergence of a threat.

The concept of risk⁴ is a means through which people understand or address dangers and uncertainties in the course of life. Risk represents the expectation of an unwanted event in relation to an external occurrence, actor, or structural condition. In this sense, risk is connected to reality and social conditions. From a security perspective, risk represents a condition that precedes the realization of threats⁵.

A threat is an opportunity for an individual or group to carry out an action that exploits a vulnerability. The term threat⁶ refers to an unwanted, intentional or unintentional event that can cause harm to a certain subject. The threat most often exploits the vulnerability of the person or object to which it is directed. Risk is the probability that a certain person or persons will be exposed to danger. Threats and risks can cause various types of harm, namely to physical integrity, territorial, moral, and legal integrity, as well as violations of norms and rules and violations of dignity. Such harm may result in injury or death, trauma, damage to homes, social relationships, values and beliefs or convictions, as well as damage to the

³Krstic, S., *Security Assessment of Threats to Certain Persons*, Millennium Group, Belgrade, 2012, p. 65.

⁴For more on risks, see: Spaseski, J., Nikolovski, M., Gerasimoski, S., *Security Systems – a Contribution to the Study of Security Systems*, Skopje, 2010.

⁵Georgieva, L.: *Risk Management*, Faculty of Philosophy, Skopje, 2006, pp. 81-83

⁶Spaseski, J., Aslimoski P., Gerasimoski, S., *Private Security* "St. Kliment Ohridski", Police Academy – Skopje, Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality – Ohrid, Skopje-Ohrid, 2008, p. 109.

natural environment, the economy and infrastructure⁷.

Risks and threats structured in this manner are qualified as general attacks or damage. For each event, it is necessary to take into account possible actions that could, in addition to hindering, interrupting, or preventing the event, escalate into large-scale destruction and cause harm to those present, to their physical and vital integrity, as well as to the other elements previously mentioned. Therefore, the need to always consider threats and risks when preparing a security plan for an event is an unavoidable and urgent task.

Whenever security issues are addressed, it is necessary to keep in mind the thought of Vladimir Vodinelić, one of the founders of criminal sciences, that it is necessary to continuously suspect and doubt every fact, phenomenon, person, and object and to expect danger. Under this assumption, mistakes in the planning phase can be avoided, which will later be reflected in the safety of the event being secured. It must always be assumed that unplanned actions may occur and may contribute to irreparable damage to the event, individuals, and the social community as a whole.

Hazard may also be understood as a component of risk. It can be categorized as natural, technical, anthropogenic (caused by a human factor), nuclear, environmental, etc. Hazard has the potential to cause serious negative impacts that may result in emergencies, crisis and catastrophe. Under such conditions, security operations take place in significantly more difficult circumstances.

Danger can be measured or assessed during the preparation of a security assessment if the elements exposed to its negative effects are identified, such as determining in which situations and during which periods the security process of the event may be endangered⁸. The more detailed the information available to the person responsible for preparing the security assessment, the greater the ability to access the negative potential of the hazard.

Therefore, in order to identify risks, threats and dangers, it is necessary to conduct a security assessment before the process of securing the event begins, more precisely during the preparation of the operational security plan. Any security assessment of event threats must start from the assumption that a certain person at the event may be attacked. First, an assessment of the overall security situation at the state level is conducted, or an assessment of the security situation in the region, municipality, or settlement, depending on the scope and nature of the event. Risk, as a future and uncertain event, can be assessed and the degree of danger arising from it can be determined, allowing for the implementation of additional security measures.

Security risk and threat assessment is an extremely important component that enables security personnel to successfully manage emerging security challenges and ensure the highest possible level of event protection. Such an assessment allows authorized officials to plan response activities in advance in the event of specific security incidents.

The purpose of developing and applying a security risk assessment is to create conditions for making efficient and effective decisions in the process of protecting the event, people, property, and operations, based on a comprehensive assessment of risks related to the entire event. This contributes to the proper protection and security of the event, as well as of all persons directly or indirectly involved in or affected by the process.

⁷Kvigin, T., *Seeing the Invisible: National Security Intelligence in an Uncertain Age*, Magor, Skopje, 2009, p. 25.

⁸Keković, Z., Bakreski, O., Stefanoski, S., Pavlović, S., "Planning and Risk Assessment for the Protection of Persons, Property and Operations", Chamber of the Republic of Macedonia for Private Security, Skopje, 2016, p. 73.

The standard risk assessment procedure consists of: identifying assets; assessing threats; assessing vulnerabilities; prioritizing risks; and determining and implementing countermeasures⁹.

Such a security assessment serves as the basis for decision-making and for the development of a security plan, that is, a document that precisely defines the measures to be undertaken to protect specific individuals. The effectiveness of security depends, among other factors, on the validity of the decisions made, which in turn depends on the quality of the assessment. This also highlights the need to improve security assessment methods and the content of security assessments. The security of individuals is based on a security threat assessment, as it provides the basis for determining the goals, tasks and bearers of protection.

As part of the preparation for making a security plan¹⁰, it is necessary to obtain (from those responsible in the agency) a sketch of the facility/facilities, with planned places or space for a certain category of persons, as well as where the other, possibly opposing audience, group of people, etc. will be located. Such information is necessary for adequate consideration in the security plan and the deployment of an appropriate number of security personnel, and later for defining the deployment model, possible shifts of personnel due to the long duration of the event, withdrawal in case of need, joint action, closure of the space, possible complete or partial evacuation, etc.

Within the framework of preparatory activities and agreements with the client/event organizer, it is necessary to define the rules for event entry or attendance. It can be an open event, where anyone can attend, attendance may be allowed with a ticket purchased from points of sale, with a pass, badge, card, ID card, uniform, insignia, etc. This method of implementation implies delegated engagement of security personnel or other persons, while the security personnel will only provide support or protection. In the event of a situation where a person does not have an appropriate "document" for entry, has lost it, has not brought it with them, or arrives ad hoc, the security personnel should know how to proceed. The presence of authorized officials from the Ministry of Interior or the organizers is also agreed upon, and clear boundaries are set for taking measures in each situation, emphasizing who is responsible, who helps, assists, who takes legal measures, who closes the space, etc. The existence of multiple entrances only complicates the overall situation and allows for an increased risk of unwanted situations occurring.

The information received, which is complete and contains information about the space, the facility, attendance, the agenda, the attendance criteria, other services authorized to attend, the supply of food, etc., as well as information related to security, fire and counter-sabotage protection, forms the basis for preparing a security plan. In addition to having operational value for the security agency and serving to properly direct the persons who are directly involved in providing security, the plan is given to the organizer so that they can be kept informed about the overall engagement of the agency. It is also mandatory to submit the plan to the regional unit of the Ministry of Interior when the event is reported.

⁹Ibid, p. 147

¹⁰Pavlovic, N., Question Models and Assessment of the Security Situation in Security Functions and the Protection of Certain Persons, specialist thesis, Criminal Police Academy, Belgrade, 2013, p. 10.

Conclusions

Regarding sports events, based on research data, we can conclude that:

- Criminal offenses that occur at sports competitions are on the rise;
- Fans are predominantly young male individuals with secondary education living in urban areas;
 - Although the security situation is generally good, with a tendency to deteriorate, and fans and the police share the same opinion, the presence of security personnel and police forces at sports competitions is mandatory;
 - When using means of coercion, the police mostly use rubber batons, while security personnel use physical force;
 - The violent behavior of fan groups at sports competitions results in a repressive attitude by the police and greater readiness of security agencies;
 - Mutual cooperation between the Macedonian police and foreign security services during international sports competitions between domestic and foreign clubs yields positive results, and the transfer of information to private security agencies is necessary, but currently insufficient, and essential for the preparation of quality and efficient security plans and their implementation;
 - There are still shortcomings in security, as at public events and sports competitions the methods of action of destructive individuals and groups are constantly changing and improving (for example, pyrotechnic devices are still being brought in by fans, sometimes in cooperation with the managements of sports clubs);
 - The work of private security agencies should move towards increased training of personnel, practicing various situations at secured events, and the procurement of sufficient and modern material and technical means and equipment;
 - There is a need for the formation of a special sector and departments in the Ministry of Interior, where specially trained units would deal with such situations in cooperation with private security agencies. In addition to practicing immediate action in the event of disturbances of public peace and order at public events or sports competitions, it is necessary to apply a proactive approach and collect operational information on all aspects of the event. This includes identifying the indirect goals of the event, the actors involved, the means by which they will act, the effect they seek to achieve, as well as the behind-the-scenes organizers of disturbances, instigators or supporters. The application of criminal intelligence and the analysis of the information obtained are necessary in order to obtain accurate, timely, usable and useful information and to avoid actions based on precisely dosed, calculated disinformation, which could further complicate the entire process of planning and implementing security at gatherings, public events, and sports competitions.

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